

Epidemiological monitoring of Gastrointestinal Helminthes of two wild Galagos: *Galagoides demidovii* and *Sciurocheirus gabonensis* (Primates, Galagidae) originated from Democratic Republic of the Congo

Jean M. Malekani¹, Koto-te-Nyiwa Ngbolua^{1,2,*}, Gladys T. Tshabu¹, Tobit L.D. Liyandja¹, Aaron L. Pambu¹, Lem's N. Kalemba¹, Fabrice B. Mwanza¹, Divin V. Malekani¹, Masengo C. Ashande², Gédéon N. Bongo^{1,3}

¹University of Kinshasa, Faculty of Science, Department of Biology, P.O. Box 190, Kinshasa, DR Congo

²Scientific Committee for Research, Conservation and the Development of Biodiversity, Faculty of Science, University of Kinshasa, D.R. Congo

³Sokoine University of Agriculture, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Department of Veterinary Microbiology and Parasitology, P.O. Box. 3015, Morogoro, Tanzania.

*Corresponding author: Koto-te-Nyiwa Ngbolua, E-mail: jpngbolua@unikin.ac.cd

Received: October 12, 2014, Accepted: November 11, 2014, Published: November 11, 2014.

ABSTRACT

Recent findings indicate that Non-human primates (NHP) serve as important reservoirs of parasites that cause diseases to man as close interactions between humans and NHP create pathways for the cross-species transmission of common zoonotic diseases. The present study was carried out with the aim of investigating the intestinal helminthes infestation in two wild species of Galagos: *Galagoides demidovii* and *Sciurocheirus gabonensis*. Stool samples collected from 30 specimens were examined from March to July 2012 using direct wet mount, concentration via sodium chloride floatation and sedimentation methods. Identification of parasitic ova was carried out according to an established protocol. Results indicated that *Hymenolepis nana* had the highest infestation rate (55.56%), followed by *Taenia* sp. (51.85%) and *Ascaris lumbricoides* (37.04%) in species from "N'djili brasserie" site while for the samples from Luki, *Taenia* sp. displayed a highest prevalence rate (75%) followed by *Ancylostoma duodenale*, *Hymenolepis nana* and *Trichostrongylus* sp. (50% each) and *Fasciola hepatica* (25%). The two types of Galagos (*Galagoides demidovii* and *Sciurocheirus gabonensis*) were infected at different levels with the cited helminthes. Regular parasitological examination as monitoring tool should be carried out to prevent zoonotic infections. For the best of our knowledge, this is the first time report on the gastrointestinal helminthes of the Congolese wild Galagos.

Keyword: *Galagoides demidovii*, *Sciurocheirus gabonensis*, helminthes, coprology

INTRODUCTION

Many of parasitic and infectious diseases are zoonotic, having shifted from wildlife populations. Wild animals constitute thus an important reservoir of a wide arrange variety of parasites and humans may be most vulnerable to diseases from non-human primates (NHP) because of their phylogenetic closeness [1]. Recent findings revealed that geographic overlap is the key factor for cross-species pathogen transmission. In Central Africa, the risk of disease transfer between wild primates and from wild primates to humans is greatest because this region was reported to contain many closely related primate species that overlap in their geographic ranges. Infecting many hosts in such hotspot ecosystem, parasites were involved in emergence of news diseases and resurgence of eradicated diseases which pose a serious and increasing threat to human health and welfare [2-5]. Human emerging infectious diseases originate from animal reservoirs are largely reported in the literature [6]. Direct contact between wild primates and humans was reported to be associated with zoonotic diseases because of their close evolutionary relationship and geographic proximity [5]. Several papers have investigated the macro-parasites of medical relevance in great apes [7-11]. Although not data on those of Congolese Galagos species are

available in the literature. These macro-parasites can however infect humans and necessitate thus an epidemiological monitoring. The present study was undertaken with the aim of investigating the gastrointestinal helminthes of two species of Galago (*Galagoides demidovii* and *Sciurocheirus gabonensis*) in order to provide the baseline data of fecal parasites.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area

Two sites of capture were chosen for this investigation. "N'djili-Brasserie" in Kinshasa city (with an average elevation above sea level/altitude of 290 m) with six stations of capture: Mona paradis touristic site (04°29'03,9'' S; 15°21'31'' E), Bonga village (04°29'8,5'' S; 15°20'26,7'' E), Lusasa forest (04°29'11,4'' S; 15°21'11,9'' E) Kimpanzu village (04°28'44,9'' S; 15°20'44,5'' E), Maman Mobutu's feminine center ground (04°28'50,9'' S; 15°21'51,3'' E), SNEL ground (04°47'43,7'' S; 015°33'40'' E) and Luki biosphere reserve located in the Western part of Democratic Republic of the Congo in the "Bas-Congo" province. The capture was made in forest at the sites located at

5°62'17,7'' S & 13°10'85,5'' E and 5°62'0,91'' S ; 13°10'72,7'' E.

Collection of samples

Faecal material examined in the present study was collected from 30 specimens of Galagos. These specimens were captured by using Tomahawk traps (figure 1G) baited with bananas. After the capture, specimens were kept in captivity at the Animal house of the Department of Biology (Centre for Animal production and health, nature conservation and development), located at the Faculty of Science, University of Kinshasa. Samples were collected between 7-9 am in March to July 2012. Top layer of fresh sample was scooped immediately after defaecation and then each sample was put in a labeled sterile bottle and kept in 10% formol. The samples were examined within 4-5 hours. The identification of the animal species was carried out according to Halternoth & Diller [12] and Kingdon [13].

Examination of samples

Samples obtained were examined using three classical methods as previously reported [10].

Direct wet smear

Wet faecal mounts with and without staining with Lugol's iodine was used to check for the presence of parasites. One gram of the faecal sample was transferred with an applicator stick unto a grease free slide. A drop of normal saline was then added and emulsified and covers with a clean cover slip. To another slide containing one gram of the faecal sample, a drop of Lugol iodine was added and viewed under the microscope using 10x and 40x objectives. Eggs were identified based on microscopic morphology.

Simple test tube floatation

One gram of sample was put into a beaker containing 50 ml floatation fluid (40% sodium chloride) and stirred thoroughly. The resulting suspension was filtered into labeled test tubes arranged in a rack. The test tubes were gently filled with the suspension leaving a convex meniscus on the top of the tube and a cover slip was carefully placed on top of the test tube and allowed to stand for 20 minutes. The cover slip was carefully lifted and immediately placed on a clean microscope slide and examined under the microscope at 10x and 40x objectives.

Sedimentation method

The sample was added to the normal saline solution, mixed, then washed and filtered through sieve into another beaker. The filter solution was poured into centrifuge tubes and centrifuged for 5 minutes at 1500 rpm using a centrifuge. The supernatant was decanted. One or two drop of the sediment was placed on microscope slide and viewed under a light microscope (XSP-C model) for identification of ova helminthes and adult helminthes.

Identification of helminthes

Helminthes were identified using the key books [14-17]. The microphotographs of ova were digitalized using computer assisted image analysis software (Motic Images 2000, version 1.3; Motic China Group Co LTD) as reported elsewhere [18-21].

RESULTS

The Table 1 gives the number and sex ratio of NHP Galagos captured during field work.

Table 1: Number and Sex ratio of NHP Galagos captured

NHP Species	N0 of specimens	Male (M)	Female (F)	Sex ratio (%)
<i>Galagoïdes demidovii</i>	30	17	13	56.6
<i>Sciurocheirus gabonensis</i>	07	06	01	14.3

Figure 1. Photographs showing: A. Eggs of *Fasciola hepatica*; B. Eggs of *Hymenolepis nana*; C. Eggs of *Taenia sp.*; D. Eggs of

Ancylostoma duodenale; E. Eggs of *Ascaris lumbricoides*; F. Eggs of *Taenia sp.*; [X500]; G. Helminthes host animal *Sciurocheirus gabonensis* (©Ngbolua et al., 2014).

It can deduce from this table that, out of 30 specimens of *Galagoïdes demidovii* captured, 17 were males and 13 females with a sex ratio (M/F) of 56.6%. Among seven specimens of *Sciurocheirus gabonensis*, six specimens were males and one female (sex ratio= 14.3%). Out of a total of 37 samples captured, only 30 animals were used for parasitic infestation analysis. Seven specimens were died in captivity.

The parasitological survey revealed that NHP were infected by 08 species of helminthes including *Hymenolepis nana*, *Taenia sp.*, *Ascaris lumbricoides*, *Ancylostoma duodenale*, *Fasciola hepatica*, *Strongyloides stercoralis*, *Trichostrongylus sp.*, and *Enterobius vermicularis*.

The photographs showing some identified eggs of helminthes and the host animal (*Sciurocheirus gabonensis*) are given figure 1.

The biological classification of the identified helminthes is given the Table 2.

Table 2. Systematic of parasites find in the digestive tracts of Galagos.

Class	Order	Family	Species	Common name
Tremada	Digenea	Fasciolidae	Fasciola hepatica	Grande douve
Cestoda	Cyclophylidea	Hymelidae	Hymenolepis nona	Taenia nain
		Taniidae	Taenia sp.	Taenia
Nematoda	Rhabdisidea	Strongylidae	Strongyloides stercoralis	Anguilule
	Ancylostomidea	Ancylostiminae	Ancylostoma duodenale	Ankylostome
		Trichostrongylidae	Trichostrongylus sp.	Trichostrongylidés
	Oxyridea	Oxyridae	Enterobius vermicularis	Oxyure
Ascaridea	Ascarididae	Ascaris lumbricoïdes	Ascaris	

The inventoried helminthes are made up of eight species found in eight families, seven orders and three classes. The class of Nematoda is the most represented with five species (62.5%), followed by the class of Cestoda (25.0%). The class of Trematoda is the less represented (12.5%).

The prevalence of helminthes according to type of Galago is shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Helminthes infestation prevalence in the NHP *Galagoïdes demidovii* and *Sciurocheirus gabonensis*

Helminthes type	Infestation rate (%)	
	<i>Galagoïdes demidovii</i> (n=26)	<i>Sciurocheirus gabonensis</i> (n=4)
<i>Ancylostoma duodenale</i>	25.30	50
<i>Ascaris lumbricoïdes</i>	37.04	0.0
<i>Enterobius vermicularis</i>	11.11	0.0
<i>Fasciola hepatica</i>	22.22	25
<i>Hymenolepis nana</i>	55.56	50
<i>Strongyloides stercoralis</i>	14.81	0.0
<i>Taenia sp.</i>	51.85	75

From the Table 3, it can deduce that, for *Galagoïdes demidovii* captured at “N’djili brasserie” the parasite infestation is high for *Hymenolepis nana*, *Taenia sp.*, *Ascaris lumbricoïdes* had the highest prevalence with respectively by 55.56%; 51.85% and 37.04%. However, *Ancylostoma duodenale*, *Fasciola hepatica*, *Strongyloides stercoralis* and *Trichostrongylus sp.* have infection rate of respectively 25.93%, 22.22% and 14.81%. This rate was lower for *Enterobius vermicularis* (11.11%). For *Sciurocheirus gabonensis* captured at “Luki station”, *Taenia sp.* displayed the high prevalence of infection (75%), followed by *Ancylostoma duodenale*, *Hymenolepsis nana* and *Trichostrongylus sp.* (50% each) and *Fasciola hepatica* (25%).

DISCUSSION

Neglected tropical diseases (NTDs) impose a heavy socio-economic burden on the poor living in Africa by aggravating poverty and social stigma in endemic communities. The goal of current control strategies is to bring these diseases to the point where they are no longer public health problems. The main NTDs of interest include helminthes zoonotic diseases particularly parasites-transmitted helminthiasis (PTHs). NHP were reported to be susceptible to many biological agents that infect human beings in particular the STHs. Thus, serving as reservoirs of PTHs, NHP can transmit disease to human (zoonotic diseases) [5]. The present study provided such evidence. Indeed, in this study, NHP were found to harbor eight different helminthes species of medical relevance for human (*Hymenolepis nana*, *Taenia sp.*, *Ascaris lumbricoïdes*, *Ancylostoma duodenale*, *Fasciola hepatica*, *Strongyloides* and *Trichostrongylus sp.*, and *Enterobius vermicularis*). Among the identified helminthes, Cestoda displayed the highest infection prevalence in both *Galagoïdes demidovii* and *Sciurocheirus gabonensis*. A similar study using other NHP like baboon and monkey as animal models

revealed the occurrence of *Trichuris trichiura* (58.06%) followed by hookworm (38.71%) and *Ascaris lumbricoïdes* (19.35%) [10]. NHP and human, sharing the same ecosystem, there is therefore possibility of inter-specific transmission of such helminthes causing thus zoonotic diseases [9, 22].

Mutani & Brown [23] reported that NHP are shareholder of the two major parasites identifying in this study. The susceptibility variation of host to parasites helminthes could be attributed to the differences in animal immune responses to the infections. For the best of our knowledge, this is the first time report on the gastrointestinal helminthes of the wild Galagos.

CONCLUSION

The present finding showed that Galagos were infected with helminthes parasites which are zoonotic. Thus, regular parasitological examination of NHP for epidemiological monitoring should be carried out to prevent zoonotic infections of humans.

REFERENCES:

1. K.L. Vigger, D.B. Lindenmayer, D.M. Spratt, 1993. The importance of disease in reintroduction programs. *Wildlife Research* 20: 687-698.
2. T.J. Davies, A.B. Pederson, 2008. Physiology and geography predict pathogen community similarity in wild primates and humans. *Proc. Boil. Sci.* 275:1695-1701.
3. T.R. Gillepsie, C.A. Chapman, 2008. Forest fragmentation, the decline of an endangered primate and changes in host-parasite interactions relative to an unfragmented forest. *American Journal of Primatology* 79: 222-230.
4. A. Herbert, 2009. Contribution à l'étude du parasitisme chez le mandrill au Gabon, Thèse de doctorat, Université

- Paul-Sabatier de Toulouse. Ecole Nationale Vétérinaire, Toulouse, France.
5. A.B. Pendersen, T.J. Davies, 2010. Cross-species pathogen transmission and disease emergence in primates. *Eco-Health*. DOI: 10.1007/s10393-010-0284-3.
 6. K.E. Jones, N. Patel, M. Levy, A. Storeygard, D. Balk, J.L. Gittleman et al., 2008. Global trends in emerging infectious diseases. *Nature* 451: 990-993.
 7. E. Munene, M. Otsyul, D.A. Mbaabu, W.T. Mutahi, S.M. Muriuki, G.M. Muchemi, 1998. Helminthes and protozoan gastrointestinal tract parasites in captive and wild-trapped African Non-human Primates. *Veterinary Parasitology* 71: 73-78.
 8. T.R. Gillepsie, E.C. Greiner, C.A. Chapman, 2005. Gastrointestinal parasites of the Colobus monkey of Uganda, *Journal of Parasitology* 91 (3): 596-573
 9. B.M. Raharivololona, and J.V. Ganzhon, 2009. Gastrointestinal parasite infection of the gray mouse Lemur (*Microcebus muricus*) in the littoral forest of Mandena, Madagascar: effects of forest fragmentation and degradation. *Madagascar Conservation and development* 4 (2): 103-112.
 10. A. Dawet, D.P Yakubu, H. M Butu, 2013. Survey of Gastrointestinal Parasites of Non-Human Primates in Jos Zoological Garden. *Journal of Primatology* 2(1): 1-3. DOI: 10.4172/2167-6801.1000108.
 11. G. N. Bichitra, I. Saidul, C. Apurba, 2012. Prevalence of parasitic infection in captive non human primates of Assam State Zoo. *India Vet. World* 5 (10): 614-616.
 12. T.H. Halternoth, H. Diller, 1985. Mammifères d’Afrique et de Madagascar. Delacaux & Nestlé, Paris, France.
 13. J. Kingdon, 2009. Guide des mammifères d’Afrique. Delachaux & Niestlé, Paris, France.
 14. C. Chapman and M.A. Huffman, 2009. Primate and their parasites, Cambridge University Press, UK.
 15. C. Chartier, I. tardj, P. Morel, 2000. Précis de parasitologie vétérinaire tropicale, TEC et Doc, Editions médicales internationales, Anvers : Belgique.
 16. OMS, 1982. Manuel des techniques de base pour le laboratoire médical, Genève : Suisse.
 17. G. Lecointre and H. Guyader, 2001. Classification phylogénétique du vivant. 3éd. Bertin, Paris : France.
 18. Ngbolua KN, Mudogo V, Mpiana PT, Malekani MJ, Rafatro Herintsoa, Urverg Ratsimamanga U, Takoy L, Rakotoarimana H, Tshibangu DST. Evaluation de l’activité anti-drépanocytaire et antipaludique de quelques taxons végétaux de la République démocratique du Congo et de Madagascar. *Ethnopharmacologia* 2013, 50: 19-24.
 19. K.N. Ngbolua, T.T. Bishola, P.T. Mpiana, V. Mudogo, D.S.T. Tshibangu, K.N. Ngombe, D.D. Tshilanda, R. Baholy, 2014. In vitro antisickling and free radical scavenging activities of *Pentaclethra macrophylla* Benth. (Fabaceae). *Journal of Advancement in Medical and Life Sciences*. V1I2. DOI: 10.15297/JALS.V1I2.03.
 20. K.N. Ngbolua, T.T. Bishola, P.T. Mpiana, V. Mudogo, D.S.T. Tshibangu, K.N. Ngombe, E.G. Ekutsu, Z.B. Gbolo, N.O. Kabena, 2014. Ethno-pharmacological survey, in vitro antisickling and free radical scavenging activities of *Carapa procera* DC. stem bark (Meliaceae). *Nova Journal of Medical and Biological Sciences* 2(2), 01-14.
 21. K.N. Ngbolua, T.T. Bishola, P.T. Mpiana, V. Mudogo, D.S.T. Tshibangu, K.N. Ngombe, E.G. Ekutsu, D.D. Tshilanda, Z.B. Gbolo, D.T. Mwanangombo, P.R. Fatiany, R. Baholy, 2014. Ethno-botanical survey, in vitro antisickling and free radical scavenging activities of *Garcinia punctata* Oliv. (Clusiaceae). *Journal of Advanced Botany & Zoology*. V1I2. DOI: 10.15297/JABZ.V1I2.04.
 22. R. Lacost, 2009. Les parasites intestinaux chez le macaque crabier (*Macaca fuscicularis*) : étude expérimentale et recommandations pour la diagnose et la gestion des rhizoflagellés et des ciliés. Thèse doctorat vétérinaire, Faculté de Médecine de CRETEIL, Ecole National Vétérinaire d’Alfort.
 23. A. Mutani, G. Brown, 2003. A preliminary investigation on the gastrointestinal helminthes of the barbodos green monkey, *Cercopithecus aethiops sabaues*. *Rev. Inst. Med. Trop. S. Paulo* 45:193-195.

Citation: Koto-te-Nyiwa Ngbolua, et al. (2014). Epidemiological monitoring of Gastrointestinal Helminthes of two wild Galagos: *Galagoides demidovii* and *Sciurocheirus gabonensis* (Primates, Galagidae) originated from Democratic Republic of the Congo. *J. of Advancement in Medical and Life Sciences*. V2I2. DOI: 10.15297/JALS.V2I2.02

Copyright: © 2014 Koto-te-Nyiwa Ngbolua. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.